

Sampling of Shape Expressions with ShapEx

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ABSTRACT

In this paper we present SHAPEx, a tool that generates random behaviors from shape expressions, a formal specification language for describing sophisticated temporal behaviors of CPS. The tool samples a random behavior in two steps: (1) it first explores the space of qualitative parameterized shapes and then (2) instantiates parameters by sampling a possibly non-linear constraint. We implement several sampling strategies in the tool that we present in the paper and demonstrate its applicability on two use scenarios.

CCS CONCEPTS

• **Theory of computation** → **Quantitative automata**; *Random search heuristics*.

KEYWORDS

shape expressions, sampling, hit-and-run, testing

1 INTRODUCTION

Cyber Physical Systems (CPS) are increasingly driven by huge amounts of data gathered by a variety of sensors and capturing multiple aspects of the system, including its physical characteristics, internal state and environment. The availability of this incredible amount of data enables new opportunities to improve the system operation. It requires analysing raw data, extracting and characterizing useful information from it – an extremely challenging task that has been mainly studied by the time-series analysis in the machine learning community [23].

Shape Expressions (SE) is a specification language for describing complex shapes encountered in time series [18]. SEs consist of regular expressions over atomic parametric shapes augmented with constraints on these parameters. SE specifications can be designed using the domain knowledge or can be automatically mined from raw time series. These specifications can represent an important artefact in documenting expected or observed behavioral patterns, in detecting anomalies and in understanding the overall system behavior.

We use the *pulse train* example, depicted in Figure 1, to illustrate a specification of sequential behaviors with SE. A pulse train is a sequence of *pulses*, where each pulse is characterized by a sequence of several segments with some constraints on the involved parameters: (A) a constant segment at some value in (4, 10) with duration in (6, 10), (B) a linearly decreasing segment with slope in (−10, −1) and duration in (1, 4), (C) another constant segment at 0 with duration in (2, 4), and two consecutive linearly increasing segments, (D) with slope in (1, 2) and duration in (0.5, 2), and (E) with slope in (5, 900) and duration in (0.01, 2). We finally also allow the concatenation of segments (D) and (E) to be replaced by a single

segment (F), a linearly increasing segment with slope in (1, 5) and duration in (2, 10). We observe that this specification uses parametric shapes, where the parameters are possibly constrained. We express the pulse train specification in SE as follows:

$$\varphi_{pulse} = (A.B.C.(D.E \text{ union } F)).A : \gamma, \text{ where}$$

$$\begin{aligned} A &= \text{line}(a_1, b_1, d_1) \\ B &= \text{line}(a_2, b_2, d_2) \\ C &= \text{line}(a_3, b_3, d_3) \\ D &= \text{line}(a_4, b_4, d_4) \\ E &= \text{line}(a_5, b_5, d_5) \\ F &= \text{line}(a_6, b_6, d_6) \\ \gamma &= a_1 = 0 \text{ and } b_1 \text{ in } (4, 10) \text{ and } d_1 \text{ in } (6, 10) \text{ and} \\ & a_2 \text{ in } (-10, -1) \text{ and } d_2 \text{ in } (1, 4) \text{ and} \\ & a_3 = 0 \text{ and } b_3 = 0 \text{ and } d_3 \text{ in } (2, 4) \text{ and} \\ & a_4 \text{ in } (1, 2) \text{ and } d_4 \text{ in } (0.5, 2) \text{ and} \\ & a_5 \text{ in } (5, 900) \text{ and } d_5 \text{ in } (0.01, 2) \text{ and} \\ & a_6 \text{ in } (1, 5) \text{ and } d_6 \text{ in } (2, 10) \text{ and } \gamma' \end{aligned}$$

where (a, b, d) denote the slope, the relative offset and the duration of a segment, respectively. In order to make sure that every segment in the sequence starts where the previous segment ends, we set γ' to the following constraint:

$$\gamma' = \text{and}_{i \in [1,4]} (b_{i+1} - a_i d_i + b_i \text{ in } (-\epsilon, +\epsilon)),$$

where ϵ is some error threshold.

We note that despite an explainable syntax, the exact meaning of the specification φ may not be self-evident. Hence, a graphical visualisation may help the designer to interpret the specification.

We also observe that SE specifications can be a valuable asset in testing CPS that operate in constrained environments. The inputs used to stimulate the system should reflect realistic environment profiles. An environment (input) profile represents a possibly infinite set of input signals subject to constraints that can be expressed in SE. For example, a constrained pulse train defined by φ_{pulse} can be used to generate test inputs that stimulate a system under test. The importance of constraining the input space was already observed in early work on hybrid systems falsification/testing [17]. More generally, it is closely related to constrained random verification initially developed for electronic designs (see for example [11, 26]), where constraints are introduced not only to ensure that the stimuli are valid or realistic (so as to avoid false negative testing results), but also to guide test executions towards critical behaviors. When there is no information about the inputs that falsify the property, it is of interest to have a more principled exploration of the input space.

In this paper, we present SHAPEx, a tool for systematic coverage-based generation of behaviors from SE specifications. The tool implements a two-stage sampling procedure: (1) it first chooses a

Figure 1: Illustrating example - a pulse train.

random word accepted by the specification with uniform distribution using the Boltzmann sampling technique [5] or a breadth-first-search based sampling algorithm; (2) in the second stage, it chooses a random parameter valuation that satisfies the constraints using a *hit-and-run* [24] sampling method. Hit-and-run is a Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) sampling method that iteratively generates a sequence of points that satisfy a constraint by taking steps of (uniformly) random length in (uniformly) random directions. Hit-and-run has several desired characteristics: (1) it can be used to sample arbitrary open sets in \mathbb{R}^n , (2) it asymptotically converges to uniform sampling, and (3) the complexity of the procedure is polynomial in the number of dimensions when the constraints are convex. We evaluate the tool using two use scenarios, visualization of specifications and test generation of inputs constrained by SEs.

2 RELATED WORK

SHAPEX implements a sampling procedure that roughly has two distinct parts: (1) random generation of qualitative (discrete) behaviors, and (2) instantiation of parameters. SHAPEX uses Boltzmann sampling [3] for the generation of discrete behaviors and implements the hit-and-run [25], a random sampling algorithm with samples that are asymptotically uniform. Apart from the *vanilla* hit-and-run algorithm, SHAPEX also implements the *shrinking* method [16] that enables better convergence in the rejection sampling of a line.

In the formal methods community, hit-and-run was investigated in the context of constraining inputs during falsification of hybrid systems [17]. Generating cyber-physical behaviors from STL using an SMT solver was proposed in [22]. Uniform sampling of timed automata models was studied in [2], where the timing behavior is subject to polytopic constraints. *Constrained random verification* (CRV) is the term used in the hardware design community to denote simulation-based verification techniques based on (uniform) sampling of constrained input spaces. Monte-Carlo LTL model-checking [9] has also a uniform sampling-based variant [20]. We finally mention the rich body of work on statistical model-checking (SMC), which is based on sampling behaviors of a system model and using statistical inference to estimate the probability that the system satisfies a property (see recent surveys [1, 12–14, 21] which include descriptions of the existing SMC tools).

3 SHAPE EXPRESSIONS

Shape expressions (SE) [19] is the formal specification language supported by SHAPEX. An SE is a regular expression over parameterized

atomic shapes (lines, sinusoids and exponentials). Atomic shapes are characterized by a set of parameters (like slope, offset or frequency) and an SE can have additional constraints over these parameters. ShapEx uses the following syntax to define the fragment of shape expressions supported by the tool.

```

atom  := line(a, b, d) | exp(a, b, c, d) | sin(a, b, c, d)
shape := atom | shape1 union shape2 | shape1 . shape2 |
        (shape)*
expr  := c | p | expr1 ± expr2 | expr1 * expr2 |
        expr1 ** expr2
cst   := expr1 > expr2 | expr1 < expr2 | cst1 and cst2
se    := shape : cst

```

Shape expressions are evaluated against finite signals that can be seen as finite sequences of (timestamp, value) pairs. A shape expression *se* consists of two main parts, a regular expression *shape* and a constraint *cst*. The regular expression *shape* captures the qualitative aspect of the specification, while *cst* contains the quantitative information of the shape expression, meaning the global constraints imposed on its parameters. The semantics of shape follows the classical semantics of regular expressions, except for the case of an atomic shape *atom*. We say that a segment of a signal defined by its starting and ending times t and t' matches an atomic shape *atom* defined over parameters (p_1, \dots, p_n) if there exists an instantiation of the atomic shape parameters such that the signal segment and the instantiated shape match.

The specification φ_{pulse} from Section 1 is an example of a shape expression and the finite signal shown in Figure 1 matches the specification. The segment of the signal defined by its start time 8 and time 10 matches the atomic shape $B = \mathbf{line}(a_2, b_2, d_2)$ with slope $a_2 = -3$, relative offset $b_2 = 6$ and duration $d_2 = 2$, while satisfying all other constraints in the specification.

4 SHAPEX METHODS AND IMPLEMENTATION

SHAPEX is an open-source library implemented in Python 3 and distributed under the BSD-3 license¹. Figure 2 depicts the overall architecture of the tool.

¹<https://github.com/figlery/ShapEx>

Figure 2: ShapEx - overview.

4.1 Parser

SHAPEx takes as input a textual SE (shape : cst) specification and translates it into three objects: (1) a parse tree of the shape, (2) its equivalent automaton representation, and (3) a parse tree of the constraint cst. The translation step is implemented using the ANTLR4 parser generator library². The resulting abstract syntax tree (AST) is converted into internal data structures (for the regular expression, its associated automaton and the constraint) over which we define visitor patterns for further exploration.

4.2 Qualitative Path Sampling

ShapEx implements two path samplers, a simple path explorer based on breadth-first search (BFS) and a more sophisticated Boltzmann sampler.

4.2.1 BFS Path Explorer. The BFS path explorer component allows sampling a path in the shape automaton. The procedure selects in a pre-processing step a set of paths using breadth-first search. This step converges when either all accepting paths have been explored (in the case that the automaton is acyclic) or when the user-specified maximum number of paths have been selected. Individual paths from this set are then drawn upon request. We note that the transitions in the selected paths are still labeled by atomic shapes, in which parameters are not yet instantiated.

4.2.2 Boltzmann Sampler. A Boltzmann sampler [5] is a procedure for randomly sampling combinatorial structures. SHAPEx implements a variant of a Boltzmann sampler for regular expressions. In the context of sampling regular languages, the Boltzmann sampler generates a word in the language of random length with the property that two words of the same length are equiprobable. The user can specify the mean length of the word that is given by the sampler.

4.3 Quantitative Parameter Sampling with Hit-and-Run

SHAPEx implements the *hit-and-run* algorithm to explore parameter constraints appearing in shape expressions. Hit-and-run is able to sample a multi-dimensional bounded open set $S \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n$. In every iteration k of the algorithm, the procedure translates the point $X_k \in S$ into another point $X_{k+1} \in S$. The generation of X_{k+1} follows several steps. First, the library chooses a random direction Θ_k in ∂D , where ∂D denotes the unit sphere in n dimensions, and then randomly chooses a point uniformly distributed on the intersection Ξ_k between the line crossing X_k along the direction Θ_k and S . The hit-and-run procedure has two non-trivial steps: (1) the initialization step, which must find the first point X_1 inside the set S , and (2) the line sampling step.

SHAPEx implements two ways to initialize the hit-and-run algorithm:

- (1) If the constraint is *linear*, *multi-affine* or *polynomial*, we encode the set S as a satisfiability-modulo theory constraint and use the Z3 constraint solver³ to find $X_1 \in S$.
- (2) For other arbitrary non-linear sets, we encode the constraint solving problem as an optimization-based search, and use a variant of the particle swarm optimization (PSO) PySwarm library⁴ to find $X_1 \in S$.

The line sampling step illustrated in Figure 3 is done by first defining an n -dimensional hyperrectangle B that encloses S . Next, we intersect the line crossing X_k along the direction Θ_k with B . The resulting line segment, denoted by $\tilde{\Xi}_k$, contains points that can be inside or outside S . We then employ 1-dimensional acceptance/rejection sampling on this line, until we get a point that is a member of S .

SHAPEx implements two optional optimizations to the classical hit-and-run algorithm:

- (1) The *shrinking* method [16] that can accelerate hit-and-run. Hit-and-run with shrinking has the same theoretical mixing

²<https://www.antlr.org/>

³<https://github.com/Z3Prover/z3>

⁴<https://pythonhosted.org/pyswarm/>

Figure 3: An illustration of hit-and-run with the bounding hyperrectangle: (1) sample X_n in S , (2) line segment \tilde{E}_n which is the intersection with B of the line with random direction Θ_n passing through X_n , (3) rejected sample X'_{n+1} on the line segment \tilde{E}_n (such that $X'_{n+1} \in B$ and $X'_{n+1} \notin S$), and (4) accepted sample X_{n+1} on the line ($X_{n+1} \in B$, $X_{n+1} \in S$).

time as without shrinking for convex sets. The efficiency of hit-and-run with shrinking is empirically superior [10].

- (2) *Coordinate directions* hit-and-run (CDHR), in which only the set of axis-aligned unit vectors is used as the set of random directions. CDHR also converges to the uniform distribution asymptotically [24] and in practice it often accelerates mixing time.

We believe that the hit-and-run implementation can have a broad interest that is independent of generating examples from shape expressions. Hence, we released the Python 3 hit-and-run implementation as an independent library under the name ANYHR and also under the BSD-3 open source license⁵. We provide an evaluation of ANYHR in Section 5.4.

4.4 Example Generator

The last component in ShapEx generates the example from the shape expression in the form of time series. It takes as input the discrete word (where each letter is a parameterized atomic shape) generated by the BFS Path Explorer or the Boltzmann Sampler, and the parameter valuation sampled by the Hit-and-Run component. It instantiates the atomic shapes with the concrete parameter values and creates a sequence of pairs (timestamp, value) that are consistent with both the discrete trace and the parameter values. A noise

⁵<https://github.com/figlerg/anyhr>

Figure 4: Visualizing the possible behaviors of the pulse shape expression with complex regular expressions structure.

is optionally added to the resulting time series, which is the main outcome of the library.

5 USE SCENARIOS

5.1 Using ShapEx

SHAPEx provides a minimal application programming interface (API) that allows simple integration and use of the library in the Python programming environment. The following block shows the simplest example of generating examples from shape expressions using SHAPEx.

```

from shapex.shapex.ShapEx import *           1
                                              2
# initialize ShapEx object                   3
se = ShapEx()                                4
# loads the specification                     5
se.add_shape_expression('pulse.se')         6
# Generate 100 examples                       7
samples = se.samples(100)                   8

```

In line 1, we first import the library. In line 4, we create a new instance of a ShapEx object (with default parameters), while in line 6, we import the specification φ_{pulse} that we encode in the file `pulse.se`. Finally, in line 8, we generate 100 signals that satisfy φ_{pulse} .

Table 1 shows parameters that can be set up by the user, with their descriptions and valid values (including the default parameter value).

5.2 Scenario 1 - Visualising Specifications

We demonstrate the use of SHAPEx to visualize and interpret specifications. We consider: (1) the pulse specification φ_{pulse} , and (2) a heart beat specification inspired from ECG signals that has thin non-linear constraints.

Figure 4 depicts 100 samples generated by ShapEx that satisfy φ_{pulse} . We observe both qualitative (number and shape of pulses) and quantitative (different parameters) variations of generated behaviors.

In the second experiment, we manually define a SE specification of a heart beat, inspired by the ECG signals from the PhysioBank database [8]. This example illustrates visualisation of non-linear specifications. The heart-beat specification is formalized as follows:

Table 1: ShapEx parameters.

Parameter	Description	Values
timestep	Difference between two consecutive timestamps.	positive float (default 1.0)
word_sampler	Qualitative word sampler.	WordSamplerMode.SEARCH (default) WordSamplerMode.BOLTZMANN
search_budget	Maximum number of distinctive qualitative words. Applicable to WordSamplerMode.SEARCH only.	positive integer (default 10)
mean_word_length	Mean length of qualitative word. Applicable to WordSamplerMode.BOLTZMANN only.	positive float (default 10.0)
dir_sampling	Direction sampling hit-and-run algorithm. Random (RDHR) vs. coordinate direction (CDHR)	DirectionSampling.RDHR (default) DirectionSampling.CDHR
shrinking	Hit-and-run with or without shrinking.	Shrinking.NO_SHINKING (default) Shrinking.SHRINKING
init_point	Finding initial point for hit-and-run. Particle swarm optimization (PSO) vs. constraint solving (SMT).	InitPoint.PSO (default) InitPoint.SMT
noise_distribution	Distribution used to add noise to the generated signals.	'uniform' (default) 'gaussian'
noise	Level of noise.	positive float (default 0.0)

$\varphi_{heart} = A \cdot B \cdot C \cdot D \cdot E \cdot F \cdot G : \gamma$, where

$$\begin{aligned}
 A &= \mathbf{exp}(a_1, b_1, c_1, d_1) \\
 B &= \mathbf{exp}(a_2, b_2, c_2, d_2) \\
 C &= \mathbf{line}(a_3, b_3, d_3) \\
 D &= \mathbf{line}(a_4, b_4, d_4) \\
 E &= \mathbf{line}(a_5, b_5, d_5) \\
 F &= \mathbf{exp}(a_6, b_6, c_6, d_6) \\
 G &= \mathbf{exp}(a_7, b_7, c_7, d_7),
 \end{aligned}$$

the constraint γ corresponds to:

$$\begin{aligned}
 &a_1 = 0 \text{ and } b_1 \text{ in } (0.008, 0.027) \text{ and} \\
 &c_1 \text{ in } (30, 32) \text{ and } d_1 \text{ in } (0.046, 0.047) \text{ and} \\
 &a_2 \text{ in } (0.03, 0.1) \text{ and } b_2 \text{ in } (0.08, 0.23) \text{ and} \\
 &c_2 \text{ in } (-35, -32) \text{ and } d_2 \text{ in } (0.101, 0.102) \\
 &a_3 \text{ in } (22, 30) \text{ and } b_3 \text{ in } (-0.12, 0.01) \text{ and } d_3 \text{ in } (0.03, 0.031) \text{ and} \\
 &a_4 \text{ in } (-50, -30) \text{ and } b_4 \text{ in } (0.7, 0.8) \text{ and } d_4 \text{ in } (0.027, 0.028) \text{ and} \\
 &a_5 \text{ in } (20, 30) \text{ and } b_5 \text{ in } (-0.4, -0.3) \text{ and } d_5 \text{ in } (0.012, 0.013) \text{ and} \\
 &a_6 \text{ in } (-0.05, 0.03) \text{ and } b_6 \text{ in } (0.018, 0.043) \text{ and} \\
 &c_6 \text{ in } (8, 9) \text{ and } d_6 \text{ in } (0.15, 0.15) \text{ and} \\
 &a_7 \text{ in } (-0.02, 0.123) \text{ and } b_7 \text{ in } (0.0395, 0.0415) \text{ and} \\
 &c_7 \text{ in } (-35, -34) \text{ and } d_7 \text{ in } (0.046, 0.047) \text{ and } \gamma'
 \end{aligned}$$

and γ' equals to:

$$\sum_{i \in \{1,2,6,7\}} (a_i * e^{**}(b_i * d_i) - a_i) + \sum_{i \in \{3,4\}} ((a_i * d_i) - a_i) \text{ in } (-\epsilon, \epsilon)$$

Due to the non-linearity of the constraints, we employ hit-and-run with PSO initialization. We also remark that the constraints of the specification are thin. We compare the performance between the classical and the coordinate direction hit-and-run to generate samples and show the results in Figure 5. In each case we generated 1000 behaviors using 1000 mixing steps. We can observe that the coordinate direction variant of the algorithm achieves much better mixing with the same number of sampled behaviors.

(a) Random direction hit-and-run

(b) Coordinate direction hit-and-run

Figure 5: Behaviors generated from φ_{heart} .

5.3 Scenario 2 - Testing with Shape Expressions and Signal Temporal Logic

We demonstrate the use of SHAPEx for systematic testing of a CPS Simulink Aircraft Elevator Control System (AECS) model [7]. A major requirement in AECS is that the intended position of the aircraft given by the pilot shall be achieved within a predefined time window and with a predetermined accuracy. The requirement

Figure 6: The pulse train as pilot command input to AECS (red) and the resulting left elevator position (blue).

states that when the Pilot Command pc has a derivative higher than some threshold m , the left actuator position lep measured by the sensor must stabilize (become at most n units away from the pilot command input) within $T + t$ time units (for some t and T).

This type of requirement can be formalized in *Signal Temporal Logic* (STL) [15], a declarative language for specifying CPS requirements. STL admits *quantitative* semantics [4, 6] that allows defining the *robustness degree* $\rho(w, \psi)$ of a STL specification ψ to a (simulation) trace w , that is, it measures how far w is from satisfying or violating ψ . We formalize this requirement as the following STL specification:

$$\psi_{stab} \equiv \square((pc' \geq m) \rightarrow \diamond_{[0,T]}\square_{[0,t]}(|pc - lep| \leq n)). \quad (1)$$

with $m = 10$, $T = 300$, $t = 50$ and $n = 0.1$.

We evaluate the following scenario - principled testing of a system-under-test (AECS model) guided by its expected properties formalized in the STL specification language (formula ψ_{stab}) under the constrained input space given by a shape expression (specification φ_{pulse}). We show how to use SHAPEx to improve: (1) simulation-based *sensitivity analysis* of the model, and (2) falsification-testing of the model.

We assume that the input (pilot command) signal is constrained with the shape expression φ_{pulse} from the introduction. Figure 6 depicts the pilot command input (in red) from Figure 1, and the resulting left elevator position output (in blue) obtained by executing the AECS model in Simulink.

In the first experiment, we sample 50 behaviors from the shape expression φ_{pulse} . To improve the uniformity of the samples' distribution, we adopt two orthogonal approaches: (1) hit-and-run with coordinate direction, and (2) accepting on average only every 100th sample. We simulate the AECS model with each of the generated input behaviors and compute robustness with respect to the STL requirement ψ_{stab} . We then study how each parameter from φ_{pulse} affect the robustness of ψ_{stab} . Figure 7 shows the results for parameters b_1 , a_2 , a_4 and a_5 . We can see that the offset b_1 at which the pulse starts and the steepness of the slope a_2 of the second segment in the pulse significantly affect the resulting robustness.

In the next experiment, we consider the falsification problem for the formula ψ_{stab} with constrained inputs:

$$\min_w \rho(w \parallel F(w), \psi_{stab}) \text{ subject to } w \in S,$$

where S is the set of constrained inputs, $w \parallel F(w)$ is the combined input (w) and output ($F(w)$) behavior of the AECS model, ψ_{stab} is an STL formula and ρ is the STL robustness function.

Figure 7: Sensitivity with respect to robustness for parameters b_1 , a_2 , a_4 and a_5 .

Figure 8: Pulse train that steers AECS to specification violation.

We consider the scenario where S is defined by the pulse-train shape expression φ_{pulse} . In every iteration, SHAPEx uses hit-and-run to generate a new candidate input that is guaranteed to satisfy the shape expression. This input behavior is used to simulate the model, and the outcome is checked for robustness. The procedure updates the current best candidate only if it reduces the robustness. In this experiment, we were able to find the input behavior that both satisfies the shape expression φ_{pulse} and steers the model to violate ψ_{stab} in 10 iterations after 32s. Figure 8 shows the input and its associated output behavior.

5.4 AnyHR Hit-and-Run Evaluation

ANYHR implements several hit-and-run variants and we evaluate them experimentally against the classical rejection sampling, denoted by rs , used as our baseline.

Our specification is defined by the n -dimensional hyper-ring: $\chi = x_1^2 + \dots + x_n^2 < c_1^2 \wedge x_1^2 + \dots + x_n^2 > c_2^2$ where $c_1 > c_2$, and the hyper-box constraint ψ embodying the hyper-ring: $\psi = \bigwedge_{i=1}^n x_i > -c \wedge x_i < c$ where $c \geq c_1$. This hyper-ring specification has the following characteristics: (1) it is polynomial, (2) it is non-convex, (3) it can be instantiated to an arbitrary number of dimensions, and (4) it can be made arbitrarily “thin”.

Figure 9: Performance of hit-and-run in number of dimensions: (1) computation time (top) and (2) acceptance rate (bottom).

We first study hit-and-run variants with respect to the number of dimensions. For this experiment, we generate 100 samples from the set defined by $\chi \wedge \psi$, where $c = c_1 = 1$ and $c_2 = 0$. We vary the number of dimensions in the specification and repeat each experiment 5 times. Figure 9 summarizes the results.

We first remark that classical rejection sampling does not scale beyond 3 dimensions. Also, the hit-and-run variants that use search fail to find an initial sample in more than 10 dimensions. The use of the SMT solver helps to efficiently find an initial sample and enables scaling to 50 dimensions. We finally observe that the shrinking mechanism allows halving the computation time (and sampling 100 points in a 100-dimensional ball in 12s) and considerably improving the acceptance rates, clearly outperforming the “vanilla” version of hit-and-run.

In the next experiment, we study the distribution of samples that it generates for hyper-rings of various thickness. In Figure 10, we visually compare the evolution of the sample distributions generated from a constraint defining a 2-dimensional ring with $c_1 = 1$ and $c_2 = 0.9$ by rejection sampling and by hit-and-run, where we take snapshots after generating 10, 50, 200 and 1000 samples.

We conduct two more experiments that evaluate the acceptance rate of hit-and-run with respect to: (1) the thickness of the hyper-ring, and (2) the size of the bounding hyper-box. In these experiments, we consider a 3-dimensional hyper-ring, in which we sample 1000 times. We repeat each experiment 5 times.

We vary the hyper-ring thickness by fixing the constants c and c_1 to 1, and by varying the value of c_2 among 0.5, 0.75, 0.9 and 0.99. Figure 11 (left) summarizes the results. We can first observe that the thinner the hyper-ring is, the closer the acceptance rate of the basic hit-and-run algorithm comes to the standard rejection

Figure 10: Evolution of sample distribution generated by hit-and-run compared to that by rejection sampling.

Figure 11: Acceptance rate with respect to the thickness of the ring (top) and to the size of the bounding box (down).

sampling. On the other hand, the shrinking mechanism allows to retain reasonable acceptance rates even for quite thin constraints (more than 10% acceptance rate when $c_1 = 1$ and $c_2 = 0.99$).

We finally fix the constants c_1 to 1 and c_2 to 0.9 and vary the size of hyperrectangles (by changing the value of c) among 1, 5, 10 and 20. The results of this experiment are summarized in Figure 11 (right). We first observe that acceptance rate of the rejection sampling procedure when $c = 5$ is only around 0.06%. We can also observe a similar trend of the acceptance rate dropping for the two hit-and-run procedures when the bounding box becomes large. We notice that the hit-and-run method with shrinking does perform better by an order of magnitude and maintains an acceptance rate above 10% when $c = 20$.

6 CONCLUSIONS

We presented SHAPEx, a tool for generating examples from formal specifications given in the form of Shape Expressions. The tool

combines model transformation, exploration of paths in automata, Boltzmann and hit-and-run sampling and example generation to enable systematic exploration of behaviors specified by shape expressions. We see many potential applications of this library, including constraint-based testing and visualization of specifications.

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